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PULMONARY VASCULAR WALL CHARACTERISTICS IN EXPERIMENTAL DIABETES MELLITUS

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This study focuses on assessing the morphofunctional condition of the pulmonary vascular endothelium in an alloxan-induced diabetes model, emphasizing its importance in understanding the effects of diabetes on the pulmonary circulatory system.

Morphometric alterations in small- and medium-caliber pulmonary vessels were examined. The findings demonstrated that alloxan-induced diabetes results in thickening of pulmonary capillary walls, reduction of vascular lumen diameter, and structural damage to endothelial cells. These pathological changes are primarily linked to endothelial dysfunction, cellular degeneration, and the cytotoxic influence of elevated glucose levels.

The study revealed that diabetes promotes interstitial edema, increased collagen accumulation, and impaired microcirculation within pulmonary blood vessels. Such morphometric alterations contribute to tissue hypoxia and disrupted pulmonary hemodynamics, representing significant complications of diabetes mellitus. The results enhance current understanding of diabetes-related pathological changes in pulmonary vascular endothelium and support the development of targeted therapeutic strategies.

Materials and Methods: The experiment was conducted on male outbred white laboratory rats weighing 170–185 g, housed under standard vivarium conditions with unrestricted access to food and water. Experimental diabetes was induced by intraperitoneal administration of alloxan (Lachema, Czechoslovakia) at a dose of 130 mg/kg following a 24-hour fasting period. Diabetes onset was confirmed through blood glucose measurement using a Contour Plus glucometer.

Morphometric evaluation of lung tissue and pulmonary vessels was performed on 116 animals at different experimental time points. Lung samples were obtained from decapitated rats. Histological sections stained with hematoxylin and eosin were analyzed to assess tissue architecture, cellular components, vascular diameters, wall thickness, and cellular damage. Digital scanning was performed using a NanoZoomer system (Hamamatsu Photonics, Japan) at 200× magnification, with data analysis conducted via automated software algorithms to minimize observer bias.

Results: Morphometric analysis demonstrated progressive structural changes in pulmonary blood vessels over 30, 60, 90, and 120 days of diabetes compared to controls.

Alveolar Capillary Endothelium Thickness: The endothelial layer of pulmonary capillaries showed a gradual increase in thickness during diabetes progression. In control animals, thickness measured $9.2 \pm 1.11 \mu\text{m}$, increasing significantly from day 30 and reaching $10.99 \pm 1.15 \mu\text{m}$ by day 120. These changes are attributed to glucose toxicity and interstitial edema.

Muscular Layer of Pulmonary Segmental Vessels: The muscular layer exhibited marked hypertrophy with disease progression. While control values averaged $28.11 \pm 1.10 \mu\text{m}$, thickness increased to $32.02 \pm 1.05 \mu\text{m}$ at 30 days and peaked at $43.04 \pm 1.01 \mu\text{m}$ by day 90, reflecting smooth muscle hyperplasia and enhanced collagen deposition.

Diameter of Pulmonary Lobular Vessels: The average diameter of primary lobular branches increased from $3.35 \pm 3.07 \text{ mm}$ in controls to $7.8 \pm 2.05 \text{ mm}$ at 120 days. Secondary branches expanded from $2.2 \pm 0.85 \text{ mm}$ to $3.1 \pm 1.84 \text{ mm}$, while tertiary branches showed milder enlargement, increasing from $1.86 \pm 2.01 \text{ mm}$ to $2.2 \pm 4.16 \text{ mm}$. These alterations reflect microcirculatory disturbances and glucose-mediated vascular remodeling.

Conclusion: Alloxan-induced diabetes leads to significant morphometric remodeling of pulmonary blood vessels, characterized by endothelial injury, vessel wall thickening, and increased vascular diameters. These changes highlight the detrimental effects of diabetes on pulmonary circulation and underscore the importance of early intervention to prevent pulmonary complications associated with diabetes mellitus.

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CERTIFICATE

SOBIROVA DILDORA

was awarded for his active participation in the scientific work on the topic

***“Pulmonary Vascular Wall Characteristics in
Experimental Diabetes Mellitus”***

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